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SUPER MoRRI – Scientific understanding and provision of an enhanced and robust monitoring system for RRI

D7.7 Summary report of exchange with SwafS funded projects related to RRI.

The SUPER MoRRI ecosystems – doing RRI together

Authors: Tjitske Holtrop, Ingeborg Meijer, Anestis Amanatidis

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Executive Summary

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) as a policy goal seeks to make a more just, inclusive, reflective, open, and responsive research and innovation (R&I) system. From the outset of the SUPER MoRRI journey, a key question is how to monitor and evaluate (M&E) RRI in a responsible way? SUPER MoRRI designed several complementary ways to answer this question. The ecosystem of projects funded under the Science with and for Society program served as one of SUPER MoRRI's data vehicles. This deliverable discusses the creation and development of the ecosystem, and the many results the ecosystem meetings yielded, among which are the meetings themselves that served as networking and informative events for the many members, the multistabilities concept categorizing the many different kinds of participating RRI projects, and the work done within the SwafS14 M&E (Monitoring and Evaluation) group focusing the evaluation of RRI such as the development of an evaluative approach called the evaluative conversations. Running through this report is an understanding of the ecosystem not only as meetings on RRI but also as RRI meetings themselves. In line with this shift, we present the conversations we had not only as conversations about monitoring and evaluating RRI, but as evaluative conversations themselves.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable

The objective of this report is to provide a description of and reflection on the ecosystem that SUPER MoRRI managed and facilitated since the fall of 2019. In the SUPER MoRRI grant agreement it was agreed that SUPER MoRRI would establish links to relevant SWAFS and RRI-related projects, with a view to analyzing and synthesizing data these projects had collected concerning the impacts of their activities and the benefits of RRI. The link originally was the MoRRI project, the common predecessor of all SwafS RRI projects. From the start, it was clear that the ‘original’ MoRRI indicators that were included in many calls of the SwafS program, needed adjustments and contextualization. Both from the contexts from other projects, and from the SUPER MoRRI developmental perspective, the ecosystem used co-creation to arrive at a common understanding and potential applicability.

This report is a reflection on three years of monthly SwafS RRI ecosystem meetings. In this deliverable we aim to describe the development of the ecosystem and its meetings. We present an understanding of the ecosystem not only as meetings on RRI but also as meetings as RRI. In line with this shift, we present the conversations we had not only as conversations about monitoring and evaluating RRI, but as evaluative conversations themselves.

1.2. Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables

Below figure 1 depicts the timing of SUPER MoRRI’s main data collection vehicles. The D7.7 Ecosystem report relates directly to deliverable D1.4 in which the future of the SUPER MoRRI monitoring framework is described. It further builds upon the First monitoring report (D2.1), where all data

vehicles are presented, and D5.4 where all pathway and pattern studies are combined.

Figure 1: Timing of data collection vehicles

The color-coding of the figure above illustrates the sequential inclusion of data from the empirical components of the Implementation Plan in the successive monitoring reports. The 1st RRI Monitoring Report (MR1) reported secondary data at the country level. MR1 covers the EU27 along with Norway and the UK. The 2nd RRI Monitoring Report (MR2) expanded on MR1 by additionally including information, data, and indicators generated by two completed large-scale studies, one of research funding organisations (RFOs) and the other of research performing organisations (RPOs). Results from a study of gendered eco-innovations and the Eurobarometer on public perceptions of research and innovation were included as well. Finally, the 3rd RRI Monitoring Report included results from a large-scale survey of researchers’ practices and perceptions in relation to RRI. It presented information and data generated as part of the project’s ongoing interactions between SUPER MoRRI and ecosystem of RRI-related projects funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 ‘Science with and for Society’ (SwafS) programme.

Like the other “data vehicles” such as the Country Correspondents RFO and RPO studies, the Researcher Survey, the Eurobarometer and other secondary data sources the SwafS ecosystem was meant to provide input for the monitoring framework from the more qualitative and experiential point of view of working with and in RRI and being involved with and in the monitoring and evaluation thereof.

1.3. Deliverable structure

This Ecosystem report is structured as follows: The Executive Summary briefly presents the purpose and contents of this report. Chapter 1 introduces the scope and objectives of the deliverable, its

relation to other tasks within the project, and its structure. Chapter 2 summarizes the development of the ecosystem. Chapter 3 clusters the SUPER MoRRI ecosystem results. Chapter 4 reflects on the process of the coming into being of the ecosystem as a RRI process in itself. And chapter 5 discusses the outreach activities of the ecosystem projects. A detailed list of ecosystem meeting content is delivered in the annex as well as a list of participating projects.

2. The ecosystem on RRI and evaluation

This report is a reflection on three years of monthly SwafS RRI ecosystem meetings. In the SUPER MoRRI grant agreement it was agreed that SUPER MoRRI would establish links to relevant SWAFS and RRI-related projects, with a view to analyzing and synthesizing data these projects had collected concerning the impacts of their activities and the benefits of RRI. The reason to follow up on the other projects funded under the Science with and for society program relates to the SUPER MoRRI predecessor, the MoRRI- project, which finished in March 2018. The basket of indicators from that project were included in many calls of the SwafS program. Hence there was a mutual benefit for all the funded projects to engage with SUPER MoRRI too, to hearing on the evolution and development of monitoring, evaluation, and indicators for RRI.

A brief word on these MoRRI indicators. The MoRRI project was tasked with implementing a monitoring system for responsible research and innovation (RRI) across its five dimensions (gender, equality, science literacy and science education, public engagement, ethics, open access/open data), and governance. Within these 6 keys, 36 indicators were developed. Consortia within the specific calls of the SwafS WP18-20 were expected to contribute to one or more MoRRI indicators. The SwafS WP18-20 was built around five strategic orientations: Accelerating and catalyzing processes of institutional change; stepping up the support to Gender Equality in Research & Innovation policy; Building the territorial dimension of SwafS partnerships; Exploring and supporting Citizen Science; and, Building the knowledge base for SwafS.

From the start the indicators were considered difficult in their application, mostly because of the difference in scale, MoRRI indicators being nationally oriented and SwafS projects situated locally or regionally. From the 36 indicators established around the 6 MoRRI keys, 6 MoRRI indicators were considered relevant, valid, feasible and useful for the consortia working under the SwafS WP 18-20 calls. These indicators (GE2, GE4, GE6, GE7, GE10, OA1) are based upon solid data-sources, most of them secondary (specifically for the gender indicators). 19 indicators could possibly remain useful albeit with modifications (GE1, GE3, GE5, GE8, GE9, SLSE2, SLSE4, PE2, PE3, PE4, PE5, PE7, PE8, OA3, OA6, E1a, E3b, GOV2, GOV3). These modifications would depend on whether the information could be retrieved at the organizational level, instead of country level.

For 8 other indicators (SLSE1, PE1, PE9, PE10, E1b, E2, E3a, GOV1) of the expected impact indicators for the other SwafS calls no indicator adjustment/data collection was foreseen. These indicators are likely to be dropped completely. The tables comparing the MoRRI indicators to the SUPER MoRRI plan are in the annex.

From the start, it was clear that these 'original' MoRRI indicators were not appropriate and would need adjustments and contextualization. Both from the contexts from other projects, and from the SUPER MoRRI developmental perspective, further conversation and co-creation was needed to arrive at a common understanding and potential applicability.

2.1. Becoming two SwafS groups

The links between the SwafS-funded projects were established in a so-called SwafS ecosystem, which met for the very first time in October 2019. After a round of introductions from the participating members of a group of RRI projects that were funded in 2018 (more projects followed in the years after) the question was discussed, what the concrete objectives for these meetings, and the ecosystem, should be. In the next few meetings, up to the summer of 2020, all projects took time to introduce themselves and their objectives. On the website of SUPER MoRRI a separate page was created.

When more projects joined, including the projects funded under call SwafS-14, the territorial RRI-projects, the discussion centered around the identification of issues demarcating regional aspects from RRI aspects. To avoid misunderstandings ecosystem members stated that territorial RRI projects require careful and tolerant balancing acts of meanings, needs and definitions. Another issue that was raised was how to use indicators, most notably the MoRRI indicators, in evaluations as evaluative formats require the use of indicators, but these rarely fit the project's context or purpose. Then, early 2020, COVID hit, and a whole session was spent on thinking through the effects of distancing policies on the work and the keys of RRI.

Over the summer of 2020 the decision was made to split the ecosystem in two groups. The regular meetings of RRI projects were maintained on a bimonthly basis as the RRI ecosystem. In these meetings ecosystem members were informed about ongoing issues in European RRI projects. On the alternating months a smaller group of 10 territorial RRI – SwafS14 – projects met to more specifically discuss issues to do with the monitoring and evaluation of these territorial RRI projects. With the aim to promote transformative R&I policy through more responsible and engaged monitoring and evaluation, these “SwafS14 M&E” meetings addressed questions such as “What does RRI look like in the territories? How do initiatives interact with territorial actors? How to evaluate the efforts towards more responsible regional and local systems of innovation?”

2.2. The RRI ecosystem

From the summer of 2020 onward, the RRI ecosystem continued with meetings and presentations every other month. In annex A the line-up of these meetings is presented. Topics that were discussed were among others Open Science; legal aspects of spreading RRI across the globe through the UNESCO 2017 Recommendation on Science and Scientific Research; citizen science; social-environmental transformative change; RRI and sustainability; and the societal readiness thinking tool. These topics were relevant to all RRI project partners.

Additionally, the ecosystem partners were approached by SUPER MORRI to get a better view on their operationalization of the concept of RRI. To this end, the research was designed in a co-creative way around these questions: how is ‘responsibility’ operationalized and how is it made measurable across the projects within the Science with and for Society program? An inquiry into 29 projects within SwafS identified three strategies through which projects operationalize responsibility and RRI in their respective contexts, namely (1) value creation for specific groups, (2) the democratization of research and innovation and (3) the mobilization of actors around RRI conceptualizations. This work was described in detail in D7.3.

2.3. The SwafS14 M&E group

The SwafS14 M&E group came together on a bimonthly basis, alternating with the RRI ecosystem, from the summer of 2020 onward as well. The intention was to discuss the possibility of a shared M&E plan for the territorial RRI-projects, cocreated with the participating SwafS14 project partners. The group assumed that collaboration between the SwafS14 projects would provide detailed information on the monitoring of regional research and innovation projects with respect to the RRI keys developed in the MoRRI project and mentioned in the original EU Horizon 2020 call: Gender Equality, Science Literacy, Public Engagement, Ethics, Open Access, and Governance (Technopolis, 2020). Other “indicators” besides these keys could be added as well, possibly reflecting conditions such as sustainability and the ‘ARRI’ process dimensions (anticipation, reflection, responsiveness, inclusion; Stilgoe, Owen, Macnaghten, 2013). Also, Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and Smart Specialization (S3)-related indicators were expected to be part of the process.

When the meetings started in the summer of 2020 some of the projects had only just started, while others had been running for some time. All projects were struggling with the effects of COVID19. Already after a few meetings, it became clear that the differences between the approaches, emphases, collaborations, or timelines of the different projects were too big to consider a one-size M&E plan to fit all projects. This became clear from a comparison of some of the M&E plans - of SISCODE, CHERRIES, TeRRItoria, and SeeRRI – and was later further explored in the four focused conversations around the four issues that each project gave substance to in its own way: RRI frameworks; evaluation practices; stakeholder engagement and indicators. These developments will be discussed in the next section.

3. Results from the ecosystem

In this section the three main results from the ecosystem are discussed: the monthly meetings, the RRI operationalization survey and report, and the focused conversations.

3.1 Ecosystem meetings

The ecosystem meetings were meant to inform members of current projects on topics in or related fields of RRI. The meetings resulted in a broader understanding of Responsible Research and Innovation as it overlaps with many other policy/reform movements such as Open Science, Citizen Science, the UNESCO Recommendations on Science and Scientific Researchers, and transformative research. In the ecosystem meetings many of these overlaps were addressed and explored, resulting in a more integrated understanding of RRI and related concepts in the world. In this section, a few of these connections between RRI and other policies are addressed.

The relationship between Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) involves promoting transparency, collaboration, and accessibility in scientific processes. Open Science emphasizes sharing research data, methods, and results openly, aligning with RRI principles that advocate for ethical considerations, inclusivity, and societal engagement in research. In Luisa Barbosa's presentation in September 2020, the overlap between Open Science and RRI was discussed in the context of the GRECO project. In November 2021 Mariana Vidal Merino from the ROSiE project zoomed in on integrity and ethics in Open Science.

Another topic brought to the ecosystem was Citizen Science. Citizen Science and RRI are closely linked as both emphasize involving and engaging citizens and civil society in the scientific process and knowledge production. Citizen Science encourages collaboration between scientists and the public, fostering a sense of shared responsibility and knowledge co-creation. RRI complements this by ensuring that citizen involvement is ethical, inclusive, and considers societal values and needs. Margaret Gold, coordinator of the Leiden Citizen Science lab, gave a talk in Jan 2021 exploring the fit between Citizen Science, RRI and Open Science.

Open Science and Citizen science not only overlap with RRI conceptually. When moving from Horizon2020 to Horizon Europe in 2021, RRI as a separate policy changed into mainstreaming RRI aspects across Horizon Europe. In its place came 'ORRI', or the general paradigm of 'Open and Responsible R&I practices', that draw on a combination of Open science, citizen science and RRI. This change in policy affected all projects represented in the Ecosystem, as they had to turn to more generic evaluative considerations, and further supported the leaving behind of the MoRRI indicators.

April Tash from UNESCO brought the "potential for spreading RRI around the globe: a few important legal steps, the related EU projects of RRING and GRRIP, and tentative next steps" to the ecosystem. Her talk was informed by the first upcoming monitoring of UNESCO's 2017 Recommendation on Science and Scientific Research (RSSR). These recommendations align with RRI in the advocacy for inclusive and equitable access to scientific knowledge. This connection emphasizes the importance of making science accessible to all, addressing global challenges collaboratively, and respecting human rights in scientific endeavors.

A last example of a topic related to RRI brought to the ecosystem was transformative research and how to assess it by Jeanne Nel from Wageningen University in September 2021. Michael Bernstein from AIT addressed a related question in September 2022 on “what can transformative innovation policy learn from responsible research and innovation?” Transformative research and RRI are interconnected as both share the goal of addressing societal challenges and ensuring positive impacts. RRI encourages transformative changes in research and innovation processes that prioritize ethical considerations, societal needs, social responsibility, and sustainability, ensuring that research and innovation contribute positively to society.

In addition to these general topics, many representatives from RRI projects presented ongoing work. Valentina Tageo presented on Multi-Act, on the design of a collective Research Impact Framework for Health RRI. Erich Griessler and Shauna Stack presented the New Horizon RRI exhibition, and Rob Smith from the university of Edinburgh presented on sustainability and RRI in the context of the project CoBioTech.

In summary, Open Science, Citizen Science, UNESCO's RSSR, and transformative research are all closely related to Responsible Research and Innovation, collectively promoting ethical, inclusive, and socially responsible scientific practices.

3.2 Multistabilities

One of the aims of the SUPER MoRRI ecosystem was to stay receptive to ongoing discussions about how to put responsibility into practice in the context of research and innovation, and how to measure it. The monthly meetings within the ecosystem yielded a wealth of knowledge about the diversity of the ways and forms in which projects put RRI into practice and measure its success. As will be discussed in the next section, there were several cross-cutting themes around the diversity of RRI concepts used to focus projects efforts and activities; the evaluative practices planned for, or not; the engagement with stakeholders which was a complicated and unstable affair; and the difficulty to put indicators to sensible use. In 2021 the ecosystem organized a survey and series of discussions around two more focused questions: How is ‘responsibility’ operationalized, and how is it made measurable across the projects within the Science with and for Society program? These discussions and the survey resulted in D7.3, the policy report on the state of SwafS RRI projects.

After an orientation in May 2021 where the initial questionnaire was shared and further developed with the ecosystem participants, the questions were sent to the whole ecosystem of 49 projects. In total 29 projects participated with a total of 36 respondents out of 110 inquiries. From the responses three strategies were identified through which projects funded under SwafS bring responsibility to life or operationalize RRI in their respective contexts. It was found that the projects base their work on one or a combination of the three understandings of RRI. These are the European Commission’s “six keys of RRI” (public engagement, ethics, gender equality, governance, open science and science education); von Schomberg’s definition of RRI as an interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the ethical acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (von Schomberg 2013); and Stilgoe, Owen and Macnaghten’s 2013 dimensions of responsible innovation of anticipation, reflection, inclusion and responsiveness.

While the projects based themselves on these established ideas of RRI, they often developed their own twists to putting responsibility into practice. Three multistabilities or understandings can be

distinguished. The concept of multistability indicates the multiple ways in which people, ambitions, resources, and strategies can come to hang together in relatively stable ways around the idea and practice of responsibility and RRI. The first multistability of “facilitating practices of responsibility” revolves around focusing on the issues and desires of a specific community or network of actors, empowering them in negotiating, establishing, and transforming issues into what for them is responsible. The role of the consortium is supportive, where resources (knowledge, network, funding etc) are offered in driving these transformations.

The second multistability of “the democratization of research and innovation” revolves around the ambition to fully democratize the research and innovation process by involving diverse sets of actors into not only the research and innovation project, but also its design. Responsibility is typically ensured through two key mechanisms: the creation of common views across all actors and the accountability of each actor for decisions and actions taken throughout the R&I process and its outcomes. These two mechanisms ensure that each actor engages fully and has the knowledge and understanding necessary to contribute to the development of the project.

The third multistability of “the mobilization of actors around RRI conceptualizations” concerns the implementation of already-existing principles or thinking of what is responsible. As opposed to the previous two stabilities, which require a proactive involvement to first declare what responsibility means in any given context, this stability provides certain normative anchor points or methodologies that, when followed, are thought to produce responsible outcomes. These pre-formulated anchor points stem from the previously described ‘6 RRI Keys’, or methodologies such as Stilgoe et al.’s dimensions (2013). Here, the strategy the projects follow is one of implementing these already-operationalised models into a specific context.

Reflecting on these multistabilities in the light of monitoring and evaluation one can see the alignment of the multistabilities with the different established understandings of RRI, such as the keys and the dimensions, which poses a challenge for monitoring and evaluation. While the MoRRI indicators or other standardization of impacts allows for comparability between projects, the diversity of the SwafS projects and their impacts escaped any standardization. Many projects therefore articulated their own indicators. The difficulties with applying established indicators to the SwafS projects lead to the thought of not only the research and project implementation should be democratized, but the evaluation of research and project implementation as well. The co-creation of indicator-development – could be a good avenue to take into account and do justice to the multiplicity of RRI in SwafS.

3.3 SwafS14 results

In this section the results from working with the subsection of the ecosystem, the SwafS14 M&E group, are discussed. This subsection consisted of 8-10 projects involved in territorial RRI and had come together to discuss the possibilities of creating a shared M&E plan. This discussion started with an analysis of some of the M&E plans of the participating projects. This analysis will be presented in the first part of this section. The analysis of the M&E plans shed some light on the main issues troubling the SwafS M&E group’s monitoring and evaluation. These main issues were the diversity of RRI frameworks, the evaluation practices, the application of indicators and stakeholder involvement. In order to explore these issues focused conversations were held that turned out to be rich and insightful. This section ends with a discussion of these focused conversations.

M&E plans

The SwafS14 M&E group came together to discuss the possibility of creating a shared M&E plan for their territorial RRI projects. In the early conversations around this topic in the second half of 2020 it very soon became clear that the differences between projects were enormous. The SwafS M&E group collectively decided to explore the differences further to see, if not a shared M&E plan, what other output or activities could follow. The SUPER MoRRI team compared three available evaluation plans – of SISCODE, TeRRitoria, and SeeRRI. In the comparison we searched for similarities and complementarities in order to be able to discuss these in the ecosystem and find shared ways of dealing and addressing these similar conditions or issues. But we also mapped the diversity in order to look for contrasts and frictions to have productive and co-creative discussions. The three projects of which we analyzed the M&E documents (SeeRRI, SIScode, and TeRRitoria) had been running for some time. Monitoring and evaluation was either included as a project intention or as a deliverable with a substantiated M&E plan. Moreover, the evaluative efforts were either incorporated into the projects as tasks or as more substantial work packages.

What are the projects about?

- **SeeRRI (2019-21)** brings together relevant actors to co-create RRI ecosystem in 3 regions (Nordland, Lower Austria, B30-Catalonia). Aim to develop a framework for integrating RRI into the regional Smart Specialisation Strategies. **Evaluation plan is a deliverable.**
- **TeRRitoria (2019-21)** aims to adapt and implement the approach of responsible research and innovation (RRI) in regional and territorial R&I systems in five European countries. Territorial RRI. **Evaluation Schema is a deliverable.**
- **SISCODE** is a three-year EU funded project within the Horizon2020 programme with 17 cross-sector partners. It aims to explore the use of co-design to operationalize RRI. **Monitoring and assessing is a task**

The comparison focused on four issues: the purposes and justification of M&E; stakeholder involvement; the approaches to M&E; and the tools and instruments applied. The three projects turned out to not have incorporated all four issues in their evaluation plans, or task descriptions.

Global justification and focus of M&E

TeRRitoria had the ambition to perform an internal evaluation of the implementation of its activities and the impacts produced through the project to ensure long term durability and sustainability of its ambitions and activities. The evaluation work package focused on tailoring an inclusive and participatory evaluation design encompassing a set of criteria/indicators suited to capture and measure institutional/regional change. Two distinct types of evaluations were envisioned:

- A process evaluation for internal learning throughout the project identifying enablers and barriers in the implementation phases.
- An impact assessment of the activities towards the end of the project.

The document addresses the substantial overlap between the purposes and tasks of several work packages and the process evaluation as the support of the territorial partners is the primary task. To support the process and maximize the outcome of the activities, it is suggested to collect evaluative data and input through already scheduled deliverables and virtual talks in order to integrate the reflective elements of the process.

SeeRRI's evaluative objectives were:

- to design methods for evaluating the project activities and the framework for self-sustaining RRI ecosystems.
- to evaluate the outcomes of the activities initiated in the three territories.
- to determine societal, democratic, environmental, economic, and scientific impacts of activities in the territories.
- to make recommendations on policy and governance structures to facilitate the creation and maintenance of self-sustaining RRI ecosystems.

The evaluation plan is very focused on defining the data collection, includes two questionnaires and discusses how to process data. Impact evaluations are generally undertaken for one or more of the following purposes: accountability, allocation, analysis, advocacy. The purpose is to demonstrate benefits and build the case for RRI.

SIScode's evaluative task is to

- Collect and interpret data from the pilots' co-creation efforts
- Provide feedback on the results of prototyping and testing phases to the internal, organizational, and institutional contexts, as well as to the regulation and policy contexts.
- The focus is on monitoring.

Stakeholder Involvement

TeRRitoria included territorial partners throughout the evaluation process to define

- the evaluation questions,
- the operational success criteria,
- objectives to be evaluated,
- and the timing and practicalities of the data collection process

TeRRitoria valued a close relation to stakeholders and practitioners in order to be able to

- increase the use and future value of the evaluation results,
- increase the democratic dimension by including a broad range of stakeholders,
- increase individual and organizational development,
- increase evaluation capacity within organizations by building internal mechanisms for continuing appraisals

The other two projects mentioned stakeholder involvement within project activities, but not for evaluative purposes.

Approaches to M&E

TeRRItoria consulted program theory (how programs work), theories of change (how and why expected changes are realized, Schwandt 2015), theories of organizational change, social science theories on globalization, and RRI. Impacts should be viewed as immediate results as well as results that take longer to materialize and in alignment with Smart Specialization Strategies. While the different activities are regarded as individual units of analysis, collectively they may provide more wide-ranging and converging knowledge on implementing and transferring the principles of RRI to a territorial level.

TeRRItoria adopted a formative evaluation approach, which is an ongoing evaluation for internal learning throughout the project, as well as an impact assessment approach or summative evaluation approach, taking place at the end of the project. The project implemented a participatory and inclusive approach that relies on partners and stakeholders to determine the criteria (and values) by which each experiment was to be evaluated in alignment with the overall experiment objectives and strategic priorities.

Process evaluation predominantly makes use of qualitative methods as the intention is to gain in-depth and interpretative knowledge on often complex processes, interactions, and perceptions. Impact evaluation may use quantitative methods.

SeeRRi worked with counterfactuals, working as control groups, in order to assess the net impact of a project or program. The measurements were taken at two different points in time, before and after the activities, to give an indication of the extent of the changes and their impacts.

The evaluation approaches include both the collection of quantitative data through questionnaires and qualitative methods such as informal interim evaluations, the collection of workshop participants' impressions via written questions or structured face-to-face interviews.

Instruments and tools

TeRRItoria used the MoRRI-indicators, the Sustainable Development Goals and RRI-indicators from the Expert Group on Policy Indicators for Responsible Research and Innovation. They used this collection as an inspirational catalogue of indicators that offers inspiration for the co-creation of context-specific success criteria and determining the material needed to document the achievement of results.

SeeRRi used a preselection of MoRRI indicators and Sustainable Development Goals.

Analysis of the MoRRI indicators (example)

Public Engagement (PE)

Item	Name of indicator	Relevant conceptual dimension at project level	Rationale for SISCODE	Notes
PE1	Models of public involvement in S&T decision making	1) Degree of formalized structures / mechanisms for involving citizens in decisions around science and technology. 2) Degree to which citizens are de facto involved in making decisions	This dimension is the basis of the co-creation journeys. Previous experience of each lab is considered in the lab's self-assessment questionnaire and then monitored in the Lab's journey spreadsheet How do we visualise the Roles of the actors in the journey?	The national level indicator was collected by the MASIS project only once in 2012. Later developments are not known. (MoRRI, 2018, p. 48)

Figure 2: Example of SIScode’s translation of the national MoRRI indicators

SIScode used the MoRRI indicators as an inspiration as well. It distilled the essential element from the indicators from MoRRI’s national level and translated it to the level of the co-creation activities, see example of figure 2.

Figure 3 provides a summary of approaches to M&E of the three projects.

M&E plans

purposes and justification	long-term durability and sustainability; framework for self-sustaining RRI ecosystems; recommendations on policy and governance structures; feedback to internal, organizational and institutional contexts; demonstration of benefits of RRI; raising awareness of potential challenges; sustainability and transferability; accountability
approaches to and aspects of M&E	problem-solving orientation; developmental evaluation; a quality orientation (evaluation is understood as a managerial procedure); a realist evaluation and co-production model; a formative process evaluation (formative evaluation, inspired by the deliberative democratic evaluation perspective); a summative impact assessment (“theory-based evaluation”); a relational approach to evaluation of social innovation; theories of change (Schwandt, 2015); theories of organizational change

M&E plans

tools and instruments applied	collect evaluative data and input through deliverables and virtual talks; evaluation questionnaires, time series; relevance/ effectiveness/ efficiency/ impact; focus on context-mechanism-outcome; implement a participatory and inclusive approach that relies on partners and stakeholders; attendants' satisfaction on involvement, degree of influence, decision making, transparency of processes, incentive mechanisms, voluntariness, implementation and perceived benefits; inspirational catalogue of indicators for the co-creation of context-specific success criteria; selection of indicators includes relevant MoRRI-indicators, Sustainable Development Goals; on-site visits; discussion/focus groups; semi-structured interviews.
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Table 1: Listing the different elements of the SwafS14 M&E plans

Some ideas from the M&E plan analysis

The discussions around the analysis of the three M&E plans of SeeRRI, TeRRitoria and SIScode made some interesting evaluative specificities visible such as SeeRRI's experimental way of evaluating, TeRRitoria's co-creation of the evaluation process and its criteria, and SIScode's translation of the MoRRI indicators from the national level to the level of local activities.

More broadly, four general differences emerged: 1) the RRI and S3 frameworks that projects drew on and aimed to integrate, 2) the diversity of stakeholders and how to engage them not only in the project as a whole, but in the evaluation activities specifically as well, 3) the evaluation practices adopted by the projects, such as how evaluation fits within the whole project, and how evaluation data collection connects to other activities. 4) the indicators, what they mean and how to use them. These four general differences were subsequently explored in four focused conversations, to be discussed in the next section.

Focused conversations

In early 2021 the "SwafS14 M&E" group organized four focused conversations around one of the issues that emerged from the M&E plan comparison. The aim was to explore these themes in smaller groups and then discuss the main takeaways in the collective SwafS14 M&E group meetings.

In the first focus group the participants were invited to reflect on how their own projects related to RRI frameworks and responsibility. The image below, taken from the RIPEET project (<http://ripeet.eu>), represents an RRI constellation based on the MoRRI keys of ethics, gender, participation, science education, open access, and governance; the RRI dimensions of anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion, and responsiveness; and the quintuple helix stakeholders of industry, academia, government, civil society, and environment. In particular, the following two questions were discussed: How to incorporate all these skills, elements, and stakeholders successfully in a project? And what kinds of RRI-inspired trajectories of change are being pursued?

From the conversation around RRI frames the diversity of approaches to RRI that the SwafS14 group consists of became immediately clear. Each project had a different focus, selection of stakeholders, ambition, each working with a different territory. Some projects had a strong focus on systemic institutional or organizational change. Others focused on citizen engagement as crucial condition for grounding RRI. Again, others argued that certain keys, such as governance, permeated all aspects of regional RRI. There was no consensus on the quintuple helix with some arguing that the environment cannot be considered as an actor. Instead, sustainability should be understood as an overarching feature of RRI within the idea of the quadruple helix. Participating researchers from all projects shared the opinion that response-able and inclusive engagement with a host of relevant, yet heterogeneous actors, concerns and languages is both the key RRI feature and key challenge for RRI.

Following the multistabilities framework by Amanatidis and Meijer in D7.3 three kinds of RRI projects were identified. The first were the projects that create value for specific societal groups. RRI projects offer resources such as knowledge, funding, and networks, encourage stakeholders to define their preferred transformations, and facilitate the process towards this direction. In such constellations, the challenge is to connect ideas and practices of RRI to the worlds of local stakeholders. The second kind of RRI project were those that focus on democratizing research and innovation, by creating common views across all actors and holding each actor equally accountable for decisions and actions taken throughout the process. For these projects it is a challenge to balance the expectations of non-consortium members, especially regarding the time and effort the engagement takes. The third kind of RRI project was concerned with mobilizing actors around already existing RRI conceptualizations. In these projects, a lot of investment is usually needed to make the RRI framework accessible to stakeholders.

The second conversation was about the engagement of stakeholders as key concern and strategy for RRI. The opinion across the participants was that engaging stakeholders effectively is not straightforward at all. Territorial RRI projects work with different kinds of stakeholders. They often involve multiple regional and non-regional partners in the project consortium who organize and manage regional coalition building. Then, there are regional stakeholders who become part of these coalitions, while having their own stakeholders as well. The focus group expressed a clear need to map the stakes of all these stakeholders and discuss how to be clear about expectations and levels of involvement.

Figure 3: RRI constellation based on RRI dimensions, MoRRI keys and quintuple helix stakeholders.

Finding and enrolling stakeholders is a complicated process. Keeping them committed for a longer period even more so. It is difficult to build trust between stakeholders; to build understanding with respect to each other's concerns and ambitions within the language of RRI; to overcome the resistance against regular assessments; and all of the above in the context of additional COVID19 restrictions. The drive to contribute to change and innovation ideally comes from the stakeholders, but this is not always the case. Commitment needs a lot of maintenance and care, communicating the benefits of

RRI and projects protocols to stakeholders and translating between stakeholders' different needs and languages.

The third conversation was about evaluation logics and practices. If conducting regional RRI projects is already complicated, then what about evaluating them? Not all projects had designed a monitoring and evaluation plan yet, or at all.

Three themes permeated the conversation about evaluation practices. In line with the other conversations, the problem of engaging stakeholders in evaluation practices existed for many. It remained a struggle to explain the benefits to stakeholders of RRI and the need for regular assessments. A second theme was the difficulty of accounting for regional differences. Many regional RRI projects weave together various interventions or forms of collective experimentation in different regions. Comparing these is difficult, and so is making quantitative statements about the changes seemingly caused by these interventions. Lastly, evaluations have several formal and informal goals and effects. Stakeholders may have different needs or opinions about these. Evaluation protocols are crucial for accountability and governance purposes, but informally monitoring and evaluating is also a way of being in touch with stakeholders, or a way of raising awareness around RRI, and a means of learning about and solving issues that are occurring in the project. Sometimes things take time to come to fruition, and at other times good things happen that were not anticipated or are not easily measurable. These phenomena escape the protocolized, formalized style of evaluation that comes in long surveys with closed-ended questions.

The problem with indicators – the subject of the last conversation – was similar to the one mentioned in the context of the previous issue. Indicators play different roles in different stages of the RRI and evaluation process. During the project they can orient partners to what might be important or needs to be addressed in the project. After the project, indicators can be used for evaluating the project or communicating project outcomes. Moreover, indicators are useful in terms of accountability and the conceptualization of new projects and funding applications. Even if indicators are not informative or useful during the project, stakeholders and project partners might still need them to account for and communicate results. A case in point have been the MoRRI indicators. The indicators derived from the MoRRI project have been included in many of the SwafS calls. Since the MoRRI indicators are oriented towards the national level, several projects struggled to use them in their regional contexts. In addition, not all projects focus on the RRI keys and consequently MoRRI indicators are not suitable for those projects. A last issue that needs mentioning, is that institutional or systemic change needs much more time than the duration of our projects. With the available indicators, these benefits of RRI, which take a long time to manifest themselves, can neither be assessed nor predicted.

The focus group conversations have been the basis for several publications and presentations authored by the collective or by (combinations of) individual members, developing ways of thinking about (territorial) RRI and its evaluation, such as the concept of the evaluative conversation, which will be discussed hereafter. This output is listed in the outreach section. The focus group conversational topics – most notably stakeholder heterogeneity and indicator use – continued to be put on the table in subsequent SwafS14 M&E meetings. In the last year of the SwafS14 M&E group meetings the group experimented with “evaluative conversations.” RRI2Scale reported on interesting experiences in this context, but also CHERRIES and RIPEET organized an ‘evaluative conversation’ with the stakeholders to address the different expectations and needs that different stakeholders of CHERRIES and RIPEET have with respect to M&E and to discuss whether or not these expectations and needs are taken into account by the cultures and structures of M&E. Additionally, the group reflected

on the co-design, co-development, and co-implementation principles developed by partner SEERRI and on whether SwafS14 M&E group members practiced the interpretations of RRI that they had come to criticize in other projects.

4. Reflection: From an ecosystem on RRI to an ecosystem as RRI

How to make sense of the meetings and conversations of the RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E group? The central issue for both groups was how to incorporate the complex context of RRI (and the associated concepts of Open Science, Citizen Science, transformative R&I) into a coherent RRI project and evaluation protocol. What resulted were three years of meetings, an understanding of responsibility put into practice with the concept of the multistabilities, and an idea of how to bring the diversity of language, contexts, stakeholders, and ambitions together in “evaluative conversations.”

4.1. Evaluative conversations

The idea of the “evaluative conversations” developed as a way to organize the monitoring and evaluation of RRI projects while giving voice to the diversity of stakeholders in RRI projects, without standardizing a protocol too rigidly as the differences between ambitions, inspirations and regions is too vast.

As has been shown in this report, the diversity of approaches to RRI of the ecosystem’s projects is enormous. Some focus on particular RRI keys, others try to incorporate as many keys as possible. Some projects work with several actors from the quintuple helix, others collaborate with only one. While everyone agrees that response-able and inclusive engagement is the key to responsible research and innovation, what this looks like in each project is wildly diverse. Then the stakeholders. These range from European bureaucrats to consortium partners, regional partners, and their stakeholders. Translating the principles and benefits of RRI for the purpose of inclusive strategy and decision making between the different stakeholder languages and concerns is in fact critical. Evaluation practices and indicators are a third dimension of the complexity of evaluating RRI. Applying indicators to the specificities of project contexts is complex if not sometimes impossible. It takes time for results to come to fruition, and at other times good things happen that were not anticipated or are not easily measurable. These phenomena escape the protocolized, formalized style of evaluations. In spite of these “referential” problems, indicators are still needed for accountability and communication purposes and funding applications.

Doing justice to the complex ambitions, bureaucratic requirements and diversity of needs and concerns of stakeholders involved was a key topic of the RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E meetings. Exploring this issue collectively brought nuance, awareness, and clarity. We started theorizing this issue as an issue of translation, of transforming the diversity of stakeholders and their needs and concerns into the bureaucratic project logic, and then back again to the needs and concerns of the stakeholders involved.

The ambition to do more careful translations required revisiting our methods and evaluative approach. Without a one-size-fits-all monitoring and evaluation plan for all regional RRI projects each RRI project would now need its own, singular M&E framework, and, consequently, project-specific data and indicators. This is in line with and even reinforces SUPER MoRRI’s “credible contextualization” guiding principle that states that there are no universal context-free indicators; indicators should be developed in ways relevant and meaningful in specific use contexts and should

pass through a co-creation phase with potential users. Moreover, the nuances of co-creation, stakeholder participation or institutional change cannot be grasped solely using complex surveys, scaling responses, or indicator sets. If the diversity that our projects encounter requires careful translation and engagement to achieve representation and ownership, we need flexibility, adaptiveness, and what we started to call “evaluative conversations” between project and territorial partners: within a project specific framework for operationalizing RRI. The remaining issue is, then, for each project to establish their own framework for operationalizing RRI and engaging in responsibility and to do this within a collective of very diverse actors.

With the idea of the “evaluative conversations” we suggest a continuous conversation between all stakeholders, from the phase of the co-definition of the central problem, to the co-development of the intervention strategy, to the co-implementation of this strategy and the co-assessment of the accomplishments. Asking at every step of the way “where do we come from?” “where do we want to go?” and “what needs to happen?” allows projects to deal with the mess and uncertainties of research and innovation, thereby connecting the often separated stakeholders and spheres of evaluation and RRI, and policy and regions. Integrating these evaluative conversations into the project’s execution allows formative, real-time evaluation to happen, building on co-creation.

4.2. The meetings

The evaluative conversations approach inevitably affected us – as ecosystem members, researchers, stakeholders, project partners – as well. Do we in fact practice what we preach? Are we attentive to difference, flexible, inclusive, and, if need be, adaptive? The grant agreement expressed the ambition for the RRI ecosystem to be a vehicle for the collection of data on the impacts of the individual projects and on the benefits of territorial RRI, in order to establish a baseline for the monitoring and evaluation of territorial RRI. While the ecosystem didn’t deliver on its promise for a data-informed baseline, a more qualitatively inspired baseline for the monitoring and evaluation of territorial RRI was in fact developed. Within the friendly, inquisitive, and supportive environment, the ecosystem members networked, explored, and exchanged inspiration and best practice. In doing this they constantly defined what (territorial) RRI and the evaluation thereof was and should be like. As such the ecosystem members themselves were in fact vehicles of sorts, refining ideas and practices of RRI in conversations, and taking the knowledge and enthusiasm forward.

Now that RRI as a term has been deleted from the language and infrastructures of the European Commission, it remains unclear what will happen with the accomplishments that were made over the past decade in the field of RRI. With the evaluative conversations approach we hope to have contributed to the sustainability of RRI as a project and an approach.

4.3. Markers of responsibility

As the ecosystem was developing the concept of evaluative conversations, in other corners of the SUPER MoRRI projects people were developing a complementary concept in parallel: markers of responsibility. This concept works well in conjunction with evaluative conversations. What is meant with the idea of markers of responsibility?

The SUPER MoRRI monitoring framework is designed as a versatile tool with strategic potential, allowing for experimentation and discrete perspectives rather than relying on a single level of analysis. It avoids indicator standardization and context-independent comparisons, offering a more nuanced

understanding of research and innovation practices. The framework consists of several markers of responsibility, below explained in their ideal way of realizing impact or benefit.

Gender Equality: The theory of change for Gender Equality (GE) emphasizes that increased representation of diverse perspectives and gender balance in research teams has intrinsic democratic value. This is expected to generate research output aligned with societal needs, leading to the alleviation of inequality and enhanced social sustainability. Despite positive developments in achieving gender balance among doctoral graduates in the EU over the last decade, women still represent only around one-third of researchers at the European level. Segregation persists in research careers, with a higher percentage of women researchers employed in the higher education sector.

Public Engagement (PE): The theory of change for Public Engagement (PE) posits that involving citizens and stakeholders in research enhances democratic values and aligns research outputs with societal needs. PE intersects with other responsibility practices such as open science and citizen science. However, data show that pathways to these benefits are complex, with institutional and disciplinary hurdles. Eurobarometer surveys indicate an increased interest in scientific discoveries in the EU populace, possibly influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic. PE activities are expected to have spillover effects onto other responsibility-related domains.

Citizen Science (CS): The theory of change for Citizen Science (CS) connects closely with PE, suggesting that CS can lead to new avenues for research and application. This benefits the Research and Innovation (R&I) system by aligning it with society, empowering citizens, and enhancing trust in science. Eurobarometer surveys suggest that the COVID-19 pandemic may have affected trust in science, with variations in trust levels for publicly and privately employed scientists. The engagement of citizens in science-related activities has shown improvement, particularly in 2020.

Open Science (OS): OS markers focus on sharing knowledge and involving others in research in an open way, aligning with societal, economic, and environmental needs. The Theory of Change for OS is similar to PE, emphasizing its intrinsic qualities and democratizing effect on the research and innovation system. While Open Access publishing has shown a rising trend, OS is less developed compared to other responsibility markers, especially in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). OS implementation is expected to evolve over time, with Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) playing a key role in promoting OS practices.

Ethics and Integrity (REI): The Theory of Change for REI stresses the intrinsic imperative and democratic value of ethical practices in the research and innovation system. Ethical considerations are expected to lead to research outputs prioritizing ethical implications. However, case studies reveal hurdles in achieving these benefits, highlighting the complexities associated with implementing ethical practices.

Sustainable Transformation and Change through Governance: While not explicitly an RRI key, interventions for sustainable social and environmental development are considered important for meeting societal needs. The Theory of Change suggests that RRI practices contribute to more sustainability. Case studies like SOLSTICE and Engaging CSOs highlight sustainability as a marker of achieving responsibility-related benefits, with a focus on ecological sustainability and climate change. Open and responsible practices are seen as instrumental in moving sustainability research beyond academia for societal and environmental benefits. Sustainability also relates to capacity building within research and stakeholder communities for social and environmental outcomes.

The SUPER MoRRI monitoring framework depends on evaluative conversations around these markers of responsibility. The translation of these markers of responsibility into ORRI practices and into institutional and organizational settings takes many forms. Often, translation simply starts with bringing together previously unrelated actors that were not or little connected before and to motivate them to collaborate. During these translations which happen along the pathway towards ORRI, several shared issues can be observed:

- the significance of culture
- the role of organization
- the importance of resources and capacities
- the challenges of interdisciplinarity
- the additional challenge of transdisciplinarity
- the theme of inequality

In the context of the evaluative conversations, these issues could be seen as prompts for the conversation: how does organizational culture impede or facilitate gender equality in responsible research and innovation? How do the challenges of interdisciplinarity enable or prevent useful public engagement? How do the presence or lack of resources and capacities make sustainable transformation possible?

The SUPER MoRRI journey has come to an end in December 2023. The project has served as an inspiration to many of the SwafS projects that had to deal with monitoring and evaluation of RRI, and reversely, these projects getting together in the monthly SwafS Ecosystem meetings have inspired SUPER MoRRI, and confirmed that diversity, translation, and context are key when discussing M&E.

Likewise, the key qualities for R&I to act open and responsibly revolves around openness towards stakeholders and the public; public and citizen participation; transparency and accountability of processes; and the governance of these aspects. The results of SUPER MORRI show how complex, slow, dynamic, and multifaceted transformative change is. Others will carry on its legacy, be it in person in their own institutes, or in the context of other Horizon Europe funded projects and European organisations to support the ERA and the Green Deal.

5. Outreach

The activities of the ecosystem were communicated through a diversity of channels, both written (in blog posts), spoken (as presentations in final events and on conferences), academic (as publication), policy-oriented in interaction with the European Commission, and through cross-collaboration as SUPER MoRRI partners were active simultaneously in other RRI-projects as well. This is listed below.

<p>Blogpost SUPER MoRRI website, Aug 2021</p>	<p><u>“One size doesn’t fit all - Evaluating SwafS projects with questionnaires”</u> (Nhien Nguyen, Felicitas Schmittinger, Tjitske Holtrop)</p> <p>Questionnaires often seem simple and straightforward means of monitoring and assessment to grasp ongoing changes and engage with people. How complex this evaluation practice turns out to be in practice! Tjitske Holtrop from the SUPERMoRRI project talked about these issues with representatives from two SwafS projects: Nhien Nguyen and Eran Vigoda-Gadot from SeeRRI (https://seerri.eu) and Alessandro Deserti, Francesca Rizzo and Felicitas Schmittinger from SISCODE (siscodeproject.eu).</p>
<p>Blogpost SUPER MoRRI website, Dec 2021</p>	<p><u>Working with and for regions: on difference</u> (Anestis Amanatidis, Norbert Steinhaus, René Wintjes)</p> <p>The European Commission’s attempts to reconcile science (‘in here’) with society (‘out there’) have created a ground swell of democratisation in European research policymaking. Accompanying this evolution is the reformulation of the action plan ‘Science and Society’ to ‘Science in Society’ in 2007, which later became ‘Science with and for Society’ (SwafS) under Horizon 2020, where participation and inclusion assume central stage as mechanisms for aligning scientific practice with ‘the needs of the real world out there’¹. The underlying assumption is that involving diverse sets of actors in research processes automatically ensures societal relevance and desirability of research outcomes. However, as participatory practices in research become further grounded, there are loud signals from the SwafS ecosystem network of SUPER MoRRI that projects experience difficulties with regards to involving diverse stakeholders. This gives rise to an introspective question: how can participation and inclusion be achieved in the context of such diverse stakeholders?</p>

<p>Blogpost, Madtrics, Sep 2022</p>	<p>CHERRIES and RIPEET: CWTS traveling the Science - Society interface (Ingeborg Meijer, Sonia Mena Jara, Anestis Amanatidis, Tim Willemse, Gaston Heimeriks)</p> <p>This blogpost presents how CWTS got involved in two H2020-funded projects, CHERRIES and RIPEET, what they are about (territorial RRI), what we have learned from it, and what our contribution was (and still is) to developing interactions between science and society.</p>
<p>Blogpost, Madtrics, Oct 2022</p>	<p>Cocreating science that society needs: introducing the EXPLORE approach (Ingeborg Meijer, Tim Willemse, Sonia Mena Jara, Anestis Amanatidis, Tjitske Holtrop, Gaston Heimeriks)</p> <p>The EXPLORE methodology was developed in the context of the two territorial RRI projects CHERRIES and RIPEET (H2020) that CWTS is participating in since 2020. It can assist territories in developing more innovative, inclusive, and self-sustaining R&I ecosystems by ensuring bottom-up involvement of all kinds of local stakeholders and citizens. This blogpost follows up on the first RIPEET CHERRIES blogpost that explains what these projects are about and what CWTS has learned from working at the science-society interface.</p>
<p>Blogpost, Madtrics, Oct 2022</p>	<p>A monitoring and evaluation framework for responsibility in R&I (Ingeborg Meijer)</p> <p>In this blogpost (and the next), the development of a Monitoring and Evaluation framework for Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in the EU is told through our learnings in the H2020-funded project SUPER MoRRI over time.</p>
<p>Blogpost, SUPER MoRRI website, Sep 2023</p>	<p>A monitoring and evaluation framework for responsibility in R&I (continued) (Ingeborg Meijer)</p> <p>In this second blogpost of the series describing the activities of the SUPER MoRRI project, we expand on the broad and global networks that the project has developed. Beyond the Country Correspondents, that were introduced in the previous blogpost, the project planned for engaging with partners working in RRI as well, the so-called Science with and for Society (SWAFS) – Ecosystem.</p>
<p>Paper fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation 2022 (53). pp. 77-84. ISSN 1726-6629</p>	<p>Evaluative conversations: translating between diverse stakeholders in regional RRI projects</p> <p>Holtrop, Tjitske and Meijer, Ingeborg and Otero-Hermida, Paula and Amanatidis, Anestis and Buongiovanni, Chiara and Casale, Donatella and Colonnello, Claudia and Deserti, Alessandro and Feudo, Fabio and Hartman, Alan and Hörlesberger, Marianne and Ipolyi, Ildiko M. and Nguyen,</p>

	<p>Nhien and Nieminen, Mika and Quinti, Gabriele and Ravn, Tine and Rizzo, Francesca and Schmittinger, Felicitas and Steinhaus, Norbert and Strand, Roger and Völker, Thomas and Wintjes, René and Yagmaei, Emad (2022). <i>fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation</i> (53). pp. 77-84. ISSN 1726-6629</p> <p>Abstract Between the summer of 2020 and the end of 2022, researchers from ten projects pertaining to the Horizon2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) call have been meeting virtually as the SwafS14 Monitoring and Evaluation ecosystem. Topics of discussion were the trials and tribulations of their regional Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) projects as well as their strategies for monitoring and evaluation. In this paper we discuss these issues as problems of translation between different kinds of stakeholders, their ambitions and languages. As we discuss the diversity and project life cycles more concretely, three translational problems of territorial RRI emerge: 1) how to engage stakeholders? 2) how to cohere diversity? And 3) 1) how to indicate accomplishments? We end with a suggestion for how to grapple with these issues: <i>evaluative conversations</i>. We hope that these conversations will facilitate more responsible and engaged monitoring and evaluation and contribute to better R&I policies.</p>
<p>RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E group gatherings</p>	<p>First SUPER MoRRI annual event 2019</p> <p>3-minute Pitches by SwafS/RRI projects SeeRRI, SISCODE, FIT4RRI, SHERPA, Big Picnic, MULTI-ACT, On-Merit, GoNano, Transform, Scivil, TeRRItoria, RRING / GRIPP, TeRRIFICA.</p>
<p>RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E group gatherings</p>	<p>CHERRIES event, May 2022</p> <p>Ecosystem discussion on how to organize institutional change in transdisciplinary contexts, in 4 categories and three layers</p> <p>There is a link to the model in: https://www.cherries2020.eu/the-new-cherries-model-is-out/</p>
<p>RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E group gatherings</p>	<p>Final SUPER MoRRI event, Brussels, 30 Nov/1 Dec 2023 Sharing of results, evaluative conversations and markers of responsibility.</p>

presentations on the RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E group	Resbios final event Dec 2022
presentations on SUPER MoRRI and ecosystems	Fit4RRI final event 2020
presentations on the RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E group	Ethna final event Nov 2022
presentations on the RRI ecosystem and SwafS14 M&E group	RRI2SCALE & TeRRIfica final event Nov 2022
presentations on SUPER MoRRI and ecosystems	Fedora final event May 2023
presentations on SUPER MoRRI and ecosystems	GRRIP final event Nov 2022
presentations on SUPER MoRRI and ecosystems	European Commission expert meeting, cluster event July 2021; Institutional changes towards open science and societal engagement in research and innovation

Table 2: Outreach activities

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Appendix I: Overview of meetings

Ecosystem 2019	Oct	At the first meeting of the SwafS ecosystem, the meeting included a round of introductions and a discussion on what the purpose of the ecosystem should be. The meeting also discussed the question of ‘translation issues’ in RRI, which includes problems in defining meanings in the context of RRI, both between different languages but also different regional, disciplinary, and epistemological contexts.
	Nov	The agenda of the second SwafS Ecosystem meeting included further elaboration on the notion of ‘translation errors’ and explicating the potential goals and objectives of the ecosystem. This ecosystem meeting also included a discussion on the ‘SR Thinking tool’, which was developed within the New HoRRizon project. The concept of a potential thesaurus of RRI was introduced, which would allow descriptions of the concepts of RRI (both defined as such and not) and would allow for learning across different contexts. It was noted that the multiplicity of meanings, needs, and definitions of RRI result in a complex balancing of mutual understanding and the tolerance of a diversity of modes of understanding RRI. A representative from the Cities-project also introduced the survey which will be conducted with various stakeholder groups during the project.
	Dec	no meeting took place
2020	Jan	During this SwafS ecosystem meeting the representatives of each project that were present described the aims and objectives of their project. The second section of the SwafS ecosystem included a description of the SUPER MoRRI project and noted feedback and questions from the participants of other projects. The questions that were posed were primarily about how secondary data sources will be interwoven and related to the other components of the project. Additionally, questions were posed regarding how the SUPER MoRRI project will be incorporating, and or moving away from the indicators that were developed within the MoRRI project.

- Feb During this SwafS ecosystem meeting, the first discussion point was a presentation by a representative of the CHERRIES project. The project will link the concepts of territorial innovation and RRI practices in the context of the healthcare innovation system. The focus of the project will be in three different national contexts, which are Murcia in Spain, Cyprus, and Örebro in Sweden. The next discussion topic included a presentation by a representative of the Co-Change project. The challenge Co-Change wishes to address is the instantiation of RRI within organizations, which contains a considerable difficult in combatting and reorienting the momentum that underlies existing practices at organizations. There is a monitoring and evaluation component of the project which will in part be based on the MoRRI indicators. What makes Co-Change a particularly noteworthy project is its spread among the quadruple helix. Partners include RPOs, RFOs, a small firm, and other associated partners. A further project that was introduced within the meeting was the SISCODE project, which stands for Co-Design for Society in innovation and science. The project is running 10 pilot projects all over Europe and uses spaces like Fablabs and museums for experimentation and exploration. Lastly, a representative from the ORBIT project introduced the self-assessment tool that was developed within the context of the project for PhD students to assess the RRI aspects of their own PhD projects.
- Mar The main discussion point of this SwafS ecosystem meeting was the Self-Assessment tool which is actively being developed within the context of the SUPER MoRRI project. A main concern of the project's aims with the tool is not to reproduce existing tools which have already been developed. The present aims of the tool is to assess RRI at the project and institutional levels. The tool is also envisioned as being a data collection vehicle which will be of use for the other components of the project. Questions were posed to the rest of the participants, such as: What would your project want to assess within an RRI self-assessment tool? What kinds of resources would your project benefit from having provided post-assessment? What context does your project envision itself benefitting from using the tool in?

- Apr The main discussion point of this SwafS ecosystem meeting consisted of discussing the ways in which the COVID-19 pandemic was reorganizing work within RRI projects and sought potential learning opportunities that might exist between the different projects. The SwafS ecosystem meeting included going through each of the various RRI keys and seeing how there may be influences on each of these as a result of the COVID pandemic. While much of the work being done within RRI projects is typically already done online, there were noticeable changes and alterations that had to be made as a consequence of the pandemic. This included acknowledging that the more informal arenas of academic work, such as conversations within hallways, meeting spaces at conferences, would no longer be possible. Alternatively, many interesting developments also occurred such novel forms of innovation like fablabs producing the code and designs to produce masks to prevent the spread of COVID. Another contentious point was the use of Zoom as a meeting platform, which early on in the pandemic was revealed to have considerable privacy flaws. A further observation made was an increasing importance being placed on the notion of 'open science', as much research on the topic of COVID was being released rapidly and in an open format.
- May The majority of this SwafS ecosystem meeting consisted of a presentation by a representative of the ORBIT project of the self-assessment tool that was developed in the context of the project. The ORBIT self-assessment tool was made with ICT researchers in mind, with the aim of encouraging and stimulating reflection on the potential ways in which PhD projects in the context of ICT 07-2020. The SwafS ecosystem meeting continued with a discussion on what kinds of lessons can be learned from the experiences of the ORBIT project in the creation, testing, and validation of their self-assessment tool.
- June no meeting took place

	July	The beginning of this SwafS Ecosystem meeting consisted of introducing the new leader of the SwafS ecosystem meetings, Tjitske Holtrop, who will be taking over the organization of the rest of the ecosystem meetings. The content of the meeting primarily consisted of introducing the concept of the Country Correspondence Network Research Funding Organization study that will be taking place as part of the SUPER MoRRI project. This component of the project consists of interviewing representatives from RFOs in different national contexts in order to understand what kinds of mechanisms they were using in terms of RRI for priority setting, funding instruments, and responsible research assessment. A separate, albeit related meeting space was also introduced, which includes the perspectives of representatives from the consortia of projects funded through SwafS 14. This meeting space is related to discussing and mutual learning in the monitoring and evaluation of the SwafS 14 projects.
SwafS14 M&E group 2020	Aug	We started up the SwafS14 M&E project, introduced all participants, discussed a project plan, time line and distribution of tasks and discussed whether and how to integrate different RRI or related frameworks.
	Oct	Discussion of the Self-Assessment questionnaire: content issues, format issues, practical issues. In the discussion we realized that we were not all in agreement or clear about the project’s missions and ambitions.
	Dec	New project plan: Analysis of policy frameworks; Analysis of M&E frameworks; Focus group discussions around certain topics; FTEval; Co-monitoring and reflection on execution of M&E
2021	Feb	Analysis of evaluation plans, follow up. Report and discussion focus group 1 on RRI frames. Report and discussion focus group 2 on evaluation practices. What comes next?
	Apr	Report and discussion focus group 3 on indicators. Report and discussion focus group 4 on stakeholders. What comes next? Fteval, “evaluative conversation” Addressing the DG for regional and urban policy
	Jun	We discussed the abstract for the Fteval conference and how to prepare for the presentation in November in Austria at the conference. Blog by Nhien and Felicitas on questionnaires. New bloggers? On the territory and regional responsibility. Discussion DG Regio: what are the lessons SwafS14 M&E would like to share with DG Regio
	Aug	no meeting took place

- Oct This meeting discussed our collective submission to the REvaluation November '21 conference in Vienna and the lessons we had drawn up to that point about monitoring and evaluating territorial RRI.
- Dec We discussed the paper we submitted to FTeval, for the REvaluation conference in November that was postponed to May 2022 because of corona. This postponement gave us the opportunity to expand and improve the paper and we discussed how and where.
- 2022 Feb Dimitrios Pontikakis (JRC) discussed the preparation of the S4 Modular Playbook. René Wintjes talked about RRI2SCALE's experimentation with "evaluative conversations. And we discussed what was going on in our ecosystem and what members would want to see addressed in the upcoming meetings.
- Apr This meeting we focused on M&E and regional RRI through the concrete context of the CHERRIES project. The purpose of this meeting was to reflect on 1) the different expectations and needs that different stakeholders of CHERRIES have with respect to M&E and on 2) whether or not these are taken into account by our cultures and structures of M&E. We organized a round-table conversation with several regional stakeholders, a project partner (our own Claudia Colonnello!) and European Commission representatives that focused around the following questions: What would make this project successful (to you)? How are these understandings of success captured? How does M&E in SwafS value these different understandings of success? Do we identify problems here? And if so, how do we move forward?
- Jun Presentation by Nhien Nguyen (SeeRRI) about co-design, co-development and co-implementation in relation to M&E. Collective discussion about co-design, co-development and co-implementation in relation to M&E.
- Oct For this meeting we organized a **focused conversation about our role as actors (researchers, facilitators, representatives...) in the fields we interact with**. We framed the problem as follows: As project partners concerned with M&E, we play a peculiar role in the contexts we monitor and evaluate: not only are we concerned about the projects' development (and their logics of planning, timing, methodology, theory...), but also the desired outcomes as expressed by policy instruments such as the promotion of RRI (or open and responsible research and innovation) in regional settings. In the conversation we turned our critical gaze towards our very own M&E activities and reflected on how we intervene in the worlds of the actors we engage and study.

	Dec	For this very last meeting we discussed some of the thoughts and ideas we co-developed over the past two and a half years and we took some time to think and talk about what worked, what we want to further develop, how and where.
RRI ecosystem 2020	Sep	Presentation by Luisa Barbosa of the GRECO guide to Open Science. Overview and discussion of the guide. Questions addressed: What are the future trends of Open Science? And, it is always hard to talk about benefits. How to approach this "romantic" or abstract idea of the benefits?
	Nov	Presentation by Dr. April Tash from UNESCO. Potential for spreading RRI around the globe: a few important legal steps, related EU projects, and tentative next steps. The main focus was on new legal agreements and EU-funded projects in SWAFS and in particular RRI and on UNESCO work in the RRING (www.rring.eu) and GRRIP (www.grrip.eu) projects.
2021	Jan	Margaret Gold, coordinator of the Leiden Citizen Science lab, gave a talk about citizen science, its characteristics, and how it fits with other policies such as RRI and Open Science.
	Mar	Valentina Tageo presented the results of the project MULTI-ACT, a SwafS 05 project on the design of a collective Research Impact Framework for Health RRI. She presented the results of the project that aimed to create and implement a new model for the effective cooperation of all relevant stakeholders. This model is applicable in defining the scope of health research as well as new metrics for the evaluation of its results. The project focused on conducting their R&I with a multi-stakeholder and co-accountable approach to reach a transformational mission.
	May	Reflection session on questions about "translating RRI" What are the forms in which RRI can travel and metamorphose into other things that may not be RRI but responsible nonetheless. A discussion about the questionnaire of 5 questions to participants of 53 RRI-related consortia.
	Jul	No meeting took place
	Sep	Presentation by Jeanne Nel, from Wageningen University, about "71 visions on our role in social-environmental transformative change." This is a study/report on the how Wageningen University can play a role in fostering transformative social-environmental change. After the presentation we discussed the connections and synergies between '71 visions' and RRI.

- Nov Anestis Amanatidis from SUPER MoRRI presented the results of the survey on “responsibility” that many of the ecosystem members participated in. Secondly, Mariana Vidal Merino from the ROSiE project presented the project which sparked a discussion around the integrity and ethics in open science.
- 2022
- Jan We discussed the ecosystem meeting agenda for the year. Additionally, Nikos Zaharis spoke about TeRRItoria’s final event.
- Mar Erich Griessler and Shauna Stack presented the New Horizon RRI exhibition. The topic of our discussion afterwards was sustainability of our RRI efforts: what is necessary to make the knowledge, results and impacts of our projects last.
- May We welcomed Irina Tiron who had just joined the EC and the ERA unit. Richard Woolley and Andre Brasil from SUPER MoRRI presented SUPER MoRRI’s RFO and RPO study and six indicators that are relevant to our contexts using the Societal Readiness Thinking Tool. We discussed several issues with regard to the translation of the SRTT to the regional stakeholders; whether all stakeholders should be involved; whether to change language; how to organize this practically.
- Sep Michael Bernstein from AIT presented a paper on the transformative ambitions of R&I. **What can transformative innovation policy learn from responsible research and innovation?** Transformative innovation frames are poised to re-shape the future of R&I policy in Europe. These idioms of science and technology governance have surged amidst the plateauing of another governance paradigm: responsible innovation. While not an extension of responsible innovation, transformative and mission-oriented frames for R&I share a common ambition to reshape science and technology relations in the interest of broad societal agendas. In this talk, we reflect on efforts to institutionalize responsible innovation and offer a provocation to transformative innovation frames—how to shape the future of S&T governance without repeating pitfalls of the past. We draw lessons from a decade of practice to show that governance of innovation—when fixed on generating changes primarily at the project level—ignores key sites of knowledge production. Drawing on extensive interviewing, participatory workshops, and auto-ethnographic reflection, we discuss the importance of looking beyond the project to other sites of science administration, and their potential role in shaping the trajectory of research and innovation policy with and for society. We conclude with a discussion of how alternative ways of shaping agenda setting, funding calls, and knowledge-production spaces and evaluations could empower actors to better realize transformative ambitions.

Nov For our final RRI ecosystem meeting we organized a discussion about **sustainability and RRI/projects**. Rob Smith, from the university of Edinburgh, gave a presentation of his thoughts on this topic after which we had a collective discussion: What does it take to let the benefits of the projects we work in last beyond the projects' duration, for the people, the region and institutions involved? How can we ensure and work on this kind of sustainability? How can we build and maintain our own RRI/ORRI knowledge and skills without reinventing the wheel each new project anew?

Appendix II: Overview of participating projects

RRI ecosystem

1	SwafS-5-2017	MULTI-ACT
2		RiConfigure
3	SwafS-5-2018-2020	Co-Change
4		ETHNA System
5		GRACE
6		GRRIP
7		RESBIOS
8	SwafS-9-2016	NewNoRRizon
9	SwafS-13-2017	SISCODE
10		RRING
11	SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020	CHERRIES
12		DigiTeRRI
13		RIPEET
14		RRI-LEADERS
15		RRI2SCALE
16		SeeRRI
17		TeRRIFICA
18		TeRRItoria
19		TetRRIS
20		TRANSFORM
21		WBC-RRI.NET
22	SwafS-15-2018-2019	ACTION
23		CitieS-Health
24		CoAct
25		CROWD4SDG
26		CSI-COP
27		EnviroCitizen
28		EU-Citizen.science
29		MICS
30		REINFORCE
31		WeCount
32	Swafs-20-2018-2019	On-MERRIT
33		C4S
34		ALLINTERACT
35		B2-inF
36		FEDORA
37	SwafS-21-2018	SUPER MoRRI
38	SwafS-22-2018	FORWARD
39	Swafs-23-2020	INCENTIVE

40		JoinUs4Health
41		TIME4CS
42	SwafS-27-2020	COESO
43		FRANCIS
44		STEP CHANGE
45		YOUCOUNT
46	SwafS-31-2020	RRistart
47		SEEDS
48		Critical Making
49		PandeVITA
50		MOSAIC
51	SwafS-19-2018-2019-2020	NEWSERA

SwafS14 M&E group

1	SwafS-21-2018	SUPER MoRRI
2	SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020	RRIZSCALE
3		SeeRRI
4		TeRRIFICA
5		TeRRItoria
6		TetRRIS
7		TRANSFORM
8		CHERRIES
9		DigiTeRRI
10		RIPEET
11	SwafS-13-2017	SISCODE

Appendix III: Comparison MoRRI Indicators to SUPER MoRRI plan

1. Which calls need to comply

The SwafS WP18-20 is built around the following five strategic orientations:

- 1- Accelerating and catalysing processes of institutional change** (Calls Swafs 01-08)
- 2- Stepping up the support to Gender Equality in Research & Innovation policy** (Calls Swafs 09-13)
- 3- Building the territorial dimension of SwafS partnerships** (Calls Swafs 14, 22)
- 4- Exploring and supporting citizen science** (Calls Swafs 15, 16)
- 5- Building the knowledge base for SwafS** (Calls Swafs 17-21)

[1] SwafS-05-2018-2019: Grounding RRI practices in research and innovation funding and performing organisations Expected Impact: Results should contribute to a greater involvement of all stakeholders in R&I, and a better and more sustainable engagement with citizens and society as a whole. Consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators, in particular GOV2 & GOV3

[1] SwafS-23-2020: Grounding RRI in society with a focus on citizen science Expected Impact: Results should contribute to a greater involvement of all stakeholders in R&I, a better and more sustainable engagement with citizens and society as a whole, and a more scientifically interested and literate society. Consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators, in particular PE5, PE7, PE8, GOV2 & GOV3

[3] SwafS-14-2018-2019: Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation Expected Impact: Consortia are expected to elaborate and implement a more open, transparent and democratic R&I system in their defined territories. Consortia are expected to evaluate their activities and provide evidence of societal, democratic, environmental, economic and scientific impacts. Involvement in the project should have a measurable transformative and opening effect on organisations involved, which should be sustainable beyond the lifetime of funding. Consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators, for instance GE1, SLSE1, SLSE4, PE1, PE2, PE5, PE7, PE8, E1, OA6, GOV2

[4] SwafS-15-2018-2019: Exploring and supporting citizen science Expected Impact: A. Coordination and Support Action: Strengthened networks, co-ordination and communication among citizen science projects. Availability of tools, guidelines, or other materials useful to actors inexperienced in organising and supporting citizen science initiatives. Increased awareness amongst the general public of citizen science. Delivery of training to citizen scientists (or potential science practitioners) and resultant increased skills, competences, and scientific excellence. Consortia should choose a basket of indicators to measure the impact of their work against. In particular, consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators, for instance PE1 to PE10

[4] SwafS-27-2020: Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation Expected Impact: a) Citizen science: Development of new scientific knowledge and/or innovations with/by citizen scientists. Evaluation evidence concerning the societal, democratic and economic costs and benefits of citizen science. Consortia should choose a basket of indicators to measure the impact of their work. In particular, consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators (for instance PE1 to PE10). B) Frugal innovation: Development of one or more frugal innovations with/by citizens. Evaluation data concerning the societal, democratic and economic costs and benefits of the frugal innovation activities. Consortia should choose a basket of indicators to measure the impact of their work. In particular, consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators (for instance PE1 to PE10)

[5] SwafS-17-2019: Consolidating and expanding the knowledge base on citizen science Expected Impact: Consortia should aim to consolidate and expand the scientific and policy knowledge base about citizen science. They should identify key incentives, disincentives, barriers and enablers to involvement of citizens and scientists. They should document, synthesise, and present evidence about the societal, democratic, economic and scientific benefits (and potential caveats) of citizen science. They should aim to impact on R&I policies by developing implementable policy recommendations and targeting them at key stakeholders. They should aim to indirectly work towards MoRRI indicators, e.g. SLSE4, PE1, PE2, PE3, PE5, PE6, PE7, PE8, PE9, PE10, OA6

[5] SwafS-18-2018: Taking stock of the application of the precautionary principle in R&I Expected Impact: Consortia are expected to contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators in particular PE 1 to 10, E 1 to 3 and GOV1 to 3

[5] SwafS-20-2018-2019: Building the SwafS knowledge base Expected Impact: Consortia should choose a basket of indicators to measure the impact of their work against. In particular, consortia are expected to contribute *to one or more of the MoRRI indicators*

[5] SwafS-31-2020: Bottom-up approach to build SwafS knowledge base Horizon 2020 Expected Impact: Consortia should choose a basket of indicators to measure the impact of their work. In particular, consortia are expected to contribute *to one or more of the MoRRI indicators*

2. What are the MoRRI indicators and are they there to stay?

Indicator	Description (colour indicates datasource)	Asked for in Swafs calls?	Replication in SUPER MoRRI?
GE1	Share of RPO's with gender equality plans	14	possibly
GE2	Share of female researchers by sector		yes
GE3	Share of RFO's promoting gender content in research		possibly
GE4	Dissimilarity Index		yes
GE5	Share of RPO's with policies to promote gender in research content		possibly
GE6	Glass Ceiling Index		yes
GE7	Gender Pay Gap		yes
GE8	Share of female heads of RPO's		possibly
GE9	Share of gender-balanced recruitment committees at RPO's		possibly
GE10	Share of female inventors and authors		yes
SLSE1	Societal aspects in Science curricula for 15-18 year old students	14	
SLSE2	RRI related training at HEI's		possibly
SLSE3	Science communication culture		
SLSE4	Citizen science activities in RPO's	14, 17	possibly
PE1	Models of public involvement in S&T decision making	14, 15, 27, 17, 18	
PE2	Policy oriented engagement with science	14, 15, 27, 17, 18	possibly
PE3	Citizen preferences for active participation in S&T decision making	15, 27, 17, 18	possibly
PE4	Active information search about controversial technology	15, 27, 18	possibly
PE5	Public engagement performance mechanisms at the level of RPO's	23, 14, 15, 27, 17, 18	possibly
PE6 (DROPPED)	Dedicated resources for public engagement	17	
PE7	Embedment of public engagement activities in the funding structure of key public research-funding agencies	23, 14, 15, 27, 17, 18	possibly
PE8	Public engagement elements as evaluative criteria in research proposal evaluations	23, 14, 15, 27, 17, 18	possibly
PE9	Research and innovation democratisation index	15, 27, 17, 18	
PE10	National infrastructure for involvement of citizens and societal actors in research and innovation	15, 27, 17, 18	
OA1	Open access literature		yes
OA2 (DROPPED)	Data publications and citations		
OA3	Social media outreach/take up of open access literature		possibly
OA4	Public perception of open access		

Indicator	Description (colour indicates datasource)	Asked for in Swafs calls?	Replication in SUPER MoRRI?
OA5	Funder mandates		
OA6	Research-performing organisations' support structures for researchers as regards incentives and barriers for data sharing	14, 17	possibly
E1a	Ethics at the level of RPO's	14, 18	possibly
E1b	Ethics at the level of RFO's (composite indicator)	14, 18	
E2	National Ethics Committees index	18	
E3a	Research-funding organisations index	18	
E3b	Research-funding organisations index (composite indicator)	18	possibly
GOV1	Use of science in policymaking	18	
GOV2	RRI-related governance mechanisms within RFO's and RPO's	5, 23, 14, 18	possibly
GOV3	RRI-related governance mechanisms within RFO's and RPO's – composite index	5, 23, 18	possibly

Datasource: orange = secondary, green = primary

So, 6 out of 36 indicators are considered relevant, valid, feasible and useful (green). These indicators are based upon solid data-sources, most of them secondary (for GE). 19 indicators possibly remain albeit with modifications. These modifications will depend on whether the information can be retrieved at the organizational level, instead of country level. For some (8) of the expected impact indicators for the other Swafs calls no indicator adjustment/data collection is foreseen (below). These indicators are likely to be dropped completely. Alternatively they may be adjusted through the SWafs ecosystem network (PE1, 10, E1, GOV1). It is remarkable that for OA and GE hardly any requirements are in the other Swafs calls, while Gender and open science are topics to be addressed.

SLSE1	Societal aspects in Science curricula for 15-18 year old students	14	
PE1	Models of public involvement in S&T decision making	14, 15, 27, 17, 18	
PE9	Research and innovation democratisation index	15, 27, 17, 18	
PE10	National infrastructure for involvement of citizens and societal actors in research and innovation	15, 27, 17, 18	
E1b	Ethics at the level of RFO's (composite indicator)	14, 18	
E2	National Ethics Committees index	18	
E3a	Research-funding organisations index	18	
GOV1	Use of science in policymaking	18	

3. Which of the indicators make sense at the organizational (meso) level

Indicator	Description (colour indicates datasource)	Replication in SUPER MoRRI?	Level (macro/meso/micro)	Data vehicle
GE1	Share of RPO's with gender equality plans	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
GE2	Share of female researchers by sector	yes	macro	Eurostat
GE3	Share of RFO's promoting gender content in research	possibly	macro	CCN RFO
GE4	Dissimilarity Index	yes	macro	SHE Figures
GE5	Share of RPO's with policies to promote gender in research content	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
GE6	Glass Ceiling Index	yes	macro	SHE Figure
GE7	Gender Wage Gap	yes	macro	Eurostat
GE8	Share of female heads of RPO's	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
GE9	Share of gender-balanced recruitment committees at RPO's	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
GE10	Share of female inventors and authors	yes	Macro/meso	WoS/Patstat
SLSE2	RRI related training at HEI's	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
SLSE4	Citizen science activities in RPO's	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
PE2	Policy oriented engagement with science	possibly	macro	Eurobarometer
PE3	Citizen preferences for active participation in S&T decision making	possibly	macro	Eurobarometer
PE4	Active information search about controversial technology	possibly	macro	Eurobarometer
PE5	Public engagement performance mechanisms at the level of RPO's	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
PE7	Embedment of public engagement activities in the funding structure of key public research-funding agencies	possibly	macro	CCN RFO
PE8	Public engagement elements as evaluative criteria in research proposal evaluations	possibly	macro	CCN RFO
OA1	Open access literature	yes	Macro/meso	WoS/Unpaywall
OA3	Social media outreach/take up of open access literature	possibly	Macro/meso	WoS altmetric.com
OA6	Research-performing organisations' support structures for researchers as regards incentives and barriers for data sharing	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
E1a	Ethics at the level of RPO's	possibly	meso	CCN RPO
E3b	Research-funding organisations index (composite indicator)	possibly	macro	CCN RFO
GOV1	Use of science in policymaking		Macro/meso	WoS Altmetric.com
GOV2	RRI-related governance mechanisms within RFO's and RPO's	possibly	Macro/meso	CCN RFO CCN RPO
GOV3	RRI-related governance mechanisms within RFO's and RPO's – composite index	possibly	Macro/meso	CCN RFO CCN RPO

Datasource: orange = secondary, green = primary

SUPER MoRRI

Scientific Understanding and Provision of an Enhanced and Robust Monitoring system for RRI Horizon 2020, Science with and for Society Work Programme 2018-2020, Topic: SwafS-21-2018 Grant Agreement Number: 824671

